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INHIBITING VARIABLES AND DISTANCE LEARNING PROGRAMMES FOR PERSONS WITH SPECIAL NEEDS IN SOUTH EASTERN NIGERIA

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with special needs aware of the advantages of engaging in the programme and making available and accessible facilities/ equipment relevant for distance learning.

Keywords - Inhibiting variables, distance learning, persons with special needs

Abstract

This study investigated the inhibiting variables and distance learning programme for persons with special needs in south East Nigeria. Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. Three research questions guided the study. The population of the study was 10 teachers with special needs working in special schools in South East Nigeria. Census sampling was adopted, hence a sample of 25 teachers with special needs was examined. The instrument for data collection was a set of questionnaire named "Inhibiting variables of the distance learning for persons with special needs, (IVODLFPWSN)" The instrument has fifteen items. It was designed along modified four-point Likert scale with response options. The instrument was face and content validated by three experts (one respectively from Special education, Guidance and counseling and Measurement and evaluation). The reliability of the instrument was determined by use of test re-test. The value deduced was .81. The research questions were answered by using means with a criterion mean score of 3.00 for decisions. It was found that non availability and accessibility of facilities/equipment and unawareness are among the perceived inhibiting variables in success of distance learning among persons with special needs. The conclusion was reached from the findings of the study. The recommendations in the study among others include making persons

Introduction

Education is indispensable for everybody. The government does not joke with it. No wonder government of Nigeria is not only responsible, but also, to a great extent, responsive to education of individuals in the country. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) declared that the educational responsibilities of the Federal Government are carried out through the Federal Ministry of Education, the 36 states Ministries of Education and the FCT Educational Secretariat as well as the 774 Local Government Education Authorities. The foregoing demonstrates the concern of the Nigeria Federal Government about education.

Education should cover both general education for persons without special need and special education for persons with special needs. The FRN (2013) perceived special education as a customized educational programme designed to meet the unique needs of persons with special needs that the general education cannot cater for. This is a pointer to the fact that persons with special needs cannot benefit from general education. In the view of Ozoji, Kolo and Ajobiewe (2012), special education refers to specifically designed instructional interventions to address the unique needs and abilities of persons with disability as well as of persons with gifts and talents. By and large the persons with special needs have unique needs

and abilities which make special arrangement for their education imperative.

The persons with special needs belong to special population. Nwachukwu cited in Maikasawa (2014) perceived child with special needs as one who:

Deviates from the ordinary child that he/she requires special attention, special services and other areas that could make life meaningful and worth living... those who require special education services in order to benefit from school curriculum. They are those who require additional help in order to achieve full education potentials within the curriculum (p.2).

It is uncovered above that they require special attention in their educational pursuit among other facets of life. Eke (2006) identified persons with special needs to include persons with visual impairment, person with hearing impairment, leaning disabled, Intellectual disabled, Speech and Language impairment, Physical and health impairment, Behaviour disorder, Multiple handicap and Gifted and Talented. Eke (2006) identified academic stress of persons with sensory impairment specifically those that are visually impaired. These are individuals among others that are identified as persons with special needs that find general education difficult to cater for as revealed above. The Nigeria Federal Ministry of Education (FRN, 2013) shall contribute to the funding of special education programme across the country and coordinate and supervise the provision of special education service and programme for persons with special needs. The same author added that there will be encouragement of national and

international donor's agency and financial institution in funding and implementing special education programmes. That follows that this special population should be taken care of any place for the purpose of their education. FRN disclosed that all necessary facilities, equipment, materials and other assistive devices that will ensure easy access to quality education of special needs persons shall be provided. Above all, FRN (2004) alerted that the education for persons with special needs shall be free at all levels and all necessary facilities that will ensure easy access to education shall be provided. The author stated there will be special training and re-training of the personal to develop capacity building to keep abreast of the latest teaching techniques, for the various categories of disabilities shall be done. It further added that Federal, State and Local governments shall fund these programs within their areas of jurisdiction.

There is now a popular mode of education to benefit everybody hopefully not excluding the persons with special needs. It is called Open and Distance Education. **Distance learning is a way of learning remotely without being in regular face-to-face contact with a teacher in the classroom** FRN (2013) stated that Open and Distance Education is the mode of education delivery

Where learners and teachers need not be in physical contact;
Which possesses high range of flexible learning environment;
That enhances access to tertiary education;
That has the capacity to deliver variety of skills; and
Which uses a variety of media and technologies to provide quality education for large number of learners (p.63).

The above showcases a wonderful mode of education that by its nature it captures persons with special needs. The goal of Open and Distance Education in Nigeria shall among others include provision of access to quality education and equity to educational opportunities, meet special needs of employers and employees by mounting special courses for employees at the workplace and encourage life-long learning opportunities (FRN, 2013). In pursuance of these goals, the Federal Government shall ensure that programmes for Open/Distance education are equivalent in status to those offered by conventional face to face mode of delivery in appropriate tertiary educational institutions, encourage and regulate the practice and strengthen the existing coordinating agencies (FRN). The foregoing is a good mode of education that ought to embrace the persons with special needs, all things being equal.

Distance learning is indeed ideal for persons with special need when the ideal in the programme is made real. This programme enables one to set one's pace of study. One takes decision as to where and when to study. A distance learning course often costs less than a full time one. There have always been efforts towards equal education opportunity for all which includes persons with special needs. There seem to be challenges for persons with special needs in benefiting from distance learning. The challenge could arise from their unique needs that differ significantly from the usual need. These individuals are identified as having special need due to their impairment, disability and handicap. Eke (2000) conceived impairment as any loss or abnormality of physical, physiological or anatomical structure or function in a person. Carter citing Ajobiewe (2014) perceived disability as any restriction or lack (resulting from an impairment) of

ability to perform an activity in the manner or within the range considered normal for human being. Ajobiewe cited World Health Organization that viewed Handicap as a disadvantage of a given individual resulting from impairment or disability that limits or prevents the fulfillment of a role that is normal. The author affirmed that one kind of impairment can cause multiple disabilities and imply several handicaps. Similarly, a certain kind of handicap can be tied to several disabilities, which, in turn, can derive from one or more impairments.

The above status of persons with special needs could inhibit their benefiting from the all-important open and distance learning programmes. It was Iheanacho (personal communication, 10th January, 2015) that asserted that persons with special needs face educational challenges that is clinically originated. By that, Iheanacho meant that educational problem of persons with special needs could have other remote causes that require clinical attention. That is to say that educational intervention alone may not be able to do the magic of helping out the challenges of persons with special needs. This could be inferred in the case of persons with special needs and how their participation in the distance learning could be inhibited.

The goal of open/distance learning is synonymous with what person with special needs desire. This is true in so far as the programme enables one to set one's pace of study. One takes decision as to where and when to study. A distance learning course often costs less than a full time one (Wikipedia, 2015). There is also the need for awareness of this special population about this popular programme. The facilities and orientation on how to use them could be an advantage to this special population in distance learning programme. There persons

with special needs teaching in primary and secondary schools in south eastern Nigeria opting for higher certificates. They may not be aware of open/ distance programme. They could enjoy the advantages derivable from there hence there are enormous advantages. More than 270,000 undergraduate students are taking their first degrees via distance learning, together with some 108,000 postgraduate students.

In recent years the advent of the internet and widespread use of the computer has led to a huge growth in distantly delivered tuition and study. **At undergraduate level, distance learning usually means students engaging with learning materials at home or work.** These materials are produced by the university, college or learning provider and are either sent directly to the student or more usually today accessed via the internet. Tutorial support is provided via a virtual learning environment, telephone, email or other electronic means. **At undergraduate level, distance learning usually means students engaging with learning materials at home or work.** This agitated the minds of the researchers to a study that focus on the inhibiting variables and distance learning programme for persons with special needs.

Statement of problem

Distance learning is very much in vogue due to its advantages to all who may find it challenging to attend conventional institutions that take full time of learners. These advantages are supposed to be enjoyed by all, especially persons with special needs. Perusal of the concept and goals of open/distance learning programme makes it imperative for learners with special needs. They are billed to enjoy the programme without any challenge or inhibitions.

It appears as though good number of persons with special needs are eager and willing to acquire higher certificates fail to do so because of how to leave their places of work and their homes and may be due to financial challenges. These persons are mainly persons with special needs teaching in primary and post primary schools. The distance learning programme takes care of some of the foregoing challenges based on the philosophy. The persons with special needs afore mentioned seem to face inhibitions. This scenario could frustrate this special population. The idea of acquiring higher certificate that can go a long way to improve their input and quality of life might be jeopardized. This could worsen the psychological state of these individuals as they continue to feel bad as a result of not enjoying what those without special needs enjoy.

No study available to the researchers had addressed the above subject matters. Other aspects of their educational challenge for inclusive education is the issues of ICT commonly excluded in their training. It is on this premise that the researchers perceived the present study as being apt and timely.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study was to investigate inhibiting variables and distance learning programmes for persons with special needs. Specifically the study sought to:

1. Find out intrinsic inhibiting factors to distance learning programme attributable (persons with special needs are responsible) to the person with special need themselves.

2. Identify extrinsic inhibiting factors (outside their making) to distance learning for persons with special needs.

Research Questions

Two research questions guided the study.

1. What are the intrinsic inhibiting factors attributable to the persons with special needs in distance learning programme?
2. What are the extrinsic inhibiting factors to the distance learning programme for persons with special needs?

Method

This study adopted descriptive survey. It used purposive sampling technique. The four oldest special education centres in Umuahia, Abia state, Abakalike, in Ebonyi state, Oji River in Enugu state and Orlu in Imo states were recognized for this study. In each of these centres in the respective states in Nigeria, all the teachers with special needs were drawn using census. It is based on that premise that in Special education centre Abia that six members of teaching staff were drawn; in Ebony centre, four members were drawn; while in Enugu, six members were drawn; and in Imo, four members were drawn. When summed, a total of ten (10) respondents were drawn. The 10 teaching staff with special needs made up the sample for the study. The instrument for data collection was a set of questionnaire named "*Inhibiting variables of the distance learning for persons with special needs, (IVODLFPWSN)*" The instrument has fourteen items. It was designed along modified four-point Likert scale with response options of *very true*, *true*, *not true* and *very untrue*. The reliability of the instrument was determined by use of test re-test. The value deduced was .83. The research

questions were answered by using means with a criterion mean score of 3.00 for decisions. Each of the copies was given to the respondents that formed the sample. For the visual impaired among them, Braille copies were made from where the research assistant was by his/her side ticked according to their response options in another print copy. Where the visually challenged prefer to be read for him/her, this is still done by the research assistant that wait a while after each item for choice option. It is through this that information/data needed were gathered among all persons with special needs that include the hearing impaired, physical and health impaired among others. In the end the inhibiting factors were elicited.

Results

Research Question One: What are the intrinsic inhibiting factors attributable to the persons with special needs in distance learning programme?

Table 1
Intrinsic inhibiting factors attributable to the persons with special needs

S/N	Items	Very true	True	Not true	Very untrue	Mean
1	My loss or damage of body parts/system essentially prevent me from benefiting from distance learning	N=8 %=80	N=2 %=20	N=0 %=0	N=0 %=0	3.8
2	I'm unable to use computers/ ICT facilities	N=7 %=70	N=3 %=30	N=0 %=0	N=0 %=0	3.7
3	My handicapping condition put me into disadvantage such that what my normal colleagues enjoy, I cannot	N=7 %=70	N=2 %=20	N=1 %=10	N=0 %=0	3.6
4	I'm not generally interested in distance learning programme	N=0 %=0	N=0 %=0	N=2 %=20	N=8 %=80	1.2
5	I'm not ready to leave my family for any	N=0 %=0	N=0 %=0	N=7 %=70	N=3 %=30	1.7
6	programme of furthering my studies again. I'm not aware of distance learning programme	N=0 N=0	N=0 N=0	N=6 N=60	N=4 N=40	1.6
7	I do not have idea that persons with special needs can benefit from distance learning programme.	N=0 %=0	N=0 %=0	N=3 %=30	N=7 %=70	1.3

The above table uncovered the intrinsic inhibiting factors attributed to the persons with special needs for distance learning programme. As indicated, the Loss or damage

of body parts/system essentially prevent the respondent benefiting from distance learning is a key inhibitor, with mean score of 3.8. In like manner, inability to use computers/ICT facilities due to their disability inhibit persons with special needs to participation in distance learning since it has mean score of 3.7. Another inhibitor shown in the table is handicapping condition prone to subjecting them to disadvantage as that which can be enjoyed by their normal colleagues may not be enjoyed by them in the programme. This foregoing item has mean score of 3.6. The three identified inhibitors originate from impairment, disability and handicap of the persons with special needs which demonstrate outstanding difference between them and those without special needs. The other items are not adjudged as inhibiting factors hence with very low mean score.

Table 2
Extrinsic inhibiting factors to the distance learning programme for persons with special needs

S/N	Items	Very true	True	Not true	Very untrue	mean
8	The government reluctance in making all the persons with special needs aware of distance learning programme.	N=8 %=80	N=2 %=20	N=0 %=0	N=0 %=0	3.8
9	Limited number of distance learning coordinating bodies.	N=7 %=70	N=3 %=30	N=0 %=0	N=0 %=0	3.7
10	Beneficiaries as persons with special needs not exposed to computer literacy by the government.	N=6 %=60	N=4 %=40	N=0 %=0	N=0 %=0	3.6
11	Very few specialists to facilitate the programme for the persons with special needs.	N=7 %=70	N=3 %=30	N=0 %=0	N=0 %=0	3.7
12	The government not being ready to fund the education of persons with special needs.	N=7 %=70	N=3 %=30	N=0 %=0	N=0 %=0	3.7
13	NGOs not being willing to sponsor the education of persons with special needs.	N=8 %=80	N=2 %=20	N=0 %=0	N=0 %=0	3.8
14	Modified format of materials/equipment for persons with special needs not being available for use in the centres.	N=7 %=70	N=2 %=20	N=1 %=10	N=0 %=0	3.2

Table 2 with seven items revealed the extrinsic inhibiting factors to the participation of persons with special needs in distance learning programme. Each of them has mean score above 3.00 which qualify them as inhibitors. The government's reluctance in ensuring awareness of the programme for all and NGOs not being willing to sponsor the

education of persons with special needs has 3.8 respectively to demonstrate as inhibitors. Three items, which are: *Limited number of distance learning coordinating bodies; Very few specialist to facilitate the programme for the persons with special needs; and the government not being ready to fund the education of persons with special needs* have mean score of 3.7 respectively. Their high mean score makes them critical inhibitors. In addition, one item, such as: *Beneficiaries as persons with special needs not exposed to computer literacy by the government* is with mean score of 3.6 to affirm its status in posing as inhibitor. Finally, one item, that is: *Modified format of materials/equipment for persons with special needs not being available for use in the centres* has mean score of 3.2 to establish its ground in being an inhibitor. The result in this table two reiterate the fact that inhibiting factors are more in extrinsic case than as they are in the intrinsic.

Discussion

One of the research questions that guided the study sought information on intrinsic in written factors of distance learning programme for persons with special needs themselves. Among those inhibitors is lost or damage of body parts or body systems that prevent essential benefit from distance learning. The finding of the study corroborate with Eke's (2000) conception impairment which is any loss or abnormality of physical, physiological or anatomical structure or function in a person. This no doubt poses challenges to persons with special needs. Therefore, the admission of persons with special needs that impairment is an inhibitor is justifiable. The other findings uncovered inability to use computer due to disabilities of persons with special needs as an intrinsic inhibitor. The finding of this study aligns with Carter cited in Ajobiewe (2014) that

perceived disability as any restriction or lack (resulting from an impairment) of ability to perform an activity in the manner or within the range considered normal for human being. This can truly pose challenge to the persons with special needs in distance learning programme. The third finding concern as inhibitor is handicapping condition that put persons with special needs at disadvantage hence they are denied what is enjoyed by normal persons. Ajobiewe cited World Health Organization viewed Handicap as a disadvantage of a given individual resulting from impairment or disability that limits or prevents the fulfillment of a role that is normal. Handicap of persons with special needs could be an inhibitor. Impairment, disability and handicap are related to both author affirmed that one kind of impairment can cause multiple disabilities and imply several handicaps. Similarly, a certain kind of handicap can be tied to several disabilities which, in turn, can derive from one or more impairments.

In the second research question the information sought was extrinsic inhibiting factors to participation of persons with special needs in distance learning programme. The government reluctance in making all the persons with special needs aware of distance learning programme was identified as inhibitor just as much as beneficiaries as persons with special needs not exposed to computer literacy by the government and NGOs not being willing to sponsor the education of persons with special needs. These inhibitors might have taken route from government carefree attitude towards the education of persons with special needs. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) declared that the educational responsibilities of the Federal Government are carried out

through the Federal Ministry of Education, the 36 states Ministries of Education and the FCT Educational Secretariat as well as the 774 Local Government Education Authorities. This remains a mere promise that has never come to reality. It was further found in the study that limited number of centres that offer distance learning to all is an extrinsic inhibitor. It was also found that very few specialists to facilitate the programme for the persons with special needs and the government not being ready to fund the education of persons with special needs. This is appalling hence FRN (2004, 2013) reiterated that the government shall make education of persons with special needs free at all levels. The author added that the government promised that all necessary facilities, equipment, materials and other assistive devices to ease access to quality of education to persons with special needs shall be provided. Modified format of materials/equipment for persons with special needs not being available for use in the centres is another extrinsic inhibiting factor. This may appear strange in view of the government promise as indicated above. The foregoing extrinsic inhibiting factors perceived by the persons with special needs are germane in view of experiences to which they have been exposed.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that intrinsic inhibiting factors to distance learning programme attributable to persons with special needs arise from their impairment, disability, and handicap. The extrinsic inhibiting factors to the persons with special needs participation in distance learning programme include lack of awareness, limited distance learning

coordinating bodies, poor computer literacy, lack of modified format of materials or equipment that can be used by persons with special needs, few specialists among facilitators, and funding problems from the government and the NGOs.

Recommendations

In view of findings of the study and conclusion reached, the following recommendations are made:

1. Persons with special needs should be made aware of open/distance learning programme by Nigerian Federal Ministry of Education with emphasis on the advantages derivable.
2. The government or NGOs or philanthropist should make effort to ensure that education is free for all persons with special needs at all levels as stipulated in National Policy on Education.
3. There should be free and compulsory distance learning programme, funded by the government, for all teaching staff with special needs in both primary and secondary schools in South Eastern Nigeria.
4. The government or NGOs should create distance learning programme for persons with special needs with a modified format in the materials and equipment they use.
5. The state and local government should contribute their quota to ensure available and accessible facilities/equipment relevant for distance learning programme.

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